

Redeuteration of Trifluoromethane in Laser Separation of Hydrogen Isotopes[†]

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The deuterium separation factors for exchange of trifluoromethane with water, hydrogen, ammonia and methane have been calculated over a wide range of temperature. From the temperature dependence of these separation factors, the corresponding enthalpies of isotopic exchange reaction have been calculated.

THE laser separation of hydrogen isotopes¹⁻³ has been attracting a great deal of attention and has generated considerable interest. Of the many systems tried on laboratory scale^{4,5}, the multi-photon dissociation of trifluoromethane by TEA-Carbon Dioxide laser⁶ offers many advantages, the foremost being the extremely high separation factors achieved in the laser dissociation, and hence it can be selected^{7,8} as a potential system for the production of heavy water on pilot plant scale⁷.

In order that any working substance can be suitably employed as the feed material for the heavy water production process based on laser separation technique, the starting material should be capable of being replenished of its depleted deuterium by any of the available, abundant source of deuterium, such as syngas, water and natural gas. As the natural abundance of deuterium in trifluoromethane is extremely low (of the order of 120 ppm), the redeuteration step assumes considerable economic importance. The redeuteration of depleted fluoroform can be achieved by the secondary source of deuterium such as water, hydrogen, methane or ammonia.

Normally, redeuteration is a fairly simple step and involves equilibration of depleted trifluoromethane with any of the above mentioned sources of hydrogen and therefore, of deuterium. For this exchange to be economically viable, the separation factors for the exchange reaction should be large and the rates of deuterium transfer should be significant. Even though separation factors for fluoroform-water system have been calculated⁹ and rates of fluoroform/DMSO and water exchange in presence of sodium hydroxide catalyst have been measured¹⁰, no information regarding deuterium separation factors or isotopic exchange rates is available regarding exchange of fluoroform with other hydrogenous sources such as hydrogen, ammonia and methane.

The purpose of the present paper is to evaluate theoretically the equilibrium constants and deuterium separation factors for the isotopic exchange reactions involving fluoroform and methane, water, hydrogen or ammonia molecule. From the knowledge of the temperature dependence of equilibrium constants for the individual reaction, corresponding enthalpy of exchange reaction can be calculated.

Theoretical :

The deuterium exchange between trifluoromethane and hydrogen, ammonia, methane and water can be represented as

If K_1 , K_2 , K_3 and K_4 represent, respectively, the equilibrium constants for the exchange reactions (1-4), it can be shown that

$$K_1 = \frac{[\text{CDF}_3][\text{CHF}_3]}{[\text{HD}][\text{H}_2]} = (1/2)\alpha_1, \quad \dots (5)$$

$$K_2 = \frac{[\text{CDF}_3][\text{CHF}_3]}{[\text{NH}_2\text{D}][\text{NH}_3]} = (1/3)\alpha_2, \quad \dots (6)$$

$$K_3 = \frac{[\text{CDF}_3][\text{CHF}_3]}{[\text{CH}_3\text{D}][\text{CH}_4]} = (1/4)\alpha_3, \quad \dots (7)$$

$$\text{and } K_4 = \frac{[\text{CDF}_3][\text{CHF}_3]}{[\text{HDO}][\text{H}_2\text{O}]} = (1/2)\alpha_4, \quad \dots (8)$$

where α_1 , α_2 , α_3 and α_4 represent the corresponding separation factors.

It has been shown by Bigeleisen and Meyer¹¹ that the equilibrium constant, K , for any isotopic exchange reaction, say,

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is given by

$$K = \frac{[A']/[A]}{[B']/[B]} = \frac{(S'/S)_B \{S/S', f [B/B']\}}{(S'/S)_A \{S/S', f [A/A']\}} \quad (10)$$

where A, A' and B, B' are the pairs of isotopic molecules, S and S' are the symmetry numbers of the isotopic species, and the quantity $\{S/S' f (A/A')\}$ is the reduced partition function ratio (RPF_R) for the pair of isotopes A and A' and reduces to^{1,2,13}

$$\{S/S' f (A/A')\} = \left[\frac{V(A)}{V(A')} \right] \quad (11)$$

where V(A) represents the vibrational partition function for a molecule A and is given by

$$V(A) = e^{-hc z_0/kT} \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{u_i}{1 - e^{-u_i}} \quad (12)$$

In eq. (12), $hc z_0$ is the zero point energy of the molecule A (z_0 expressed in cm^{-1}) and u_i is defined as

$$u_i = \frac{hc \omega_i}{kT} = 1.4385 \frac{\omega_i}{T} \quad (13)$$

where ω_i is the fundamental harmonic frequency of vibration of the i th mode, T the absolute temperature and n the total number of vibrational modes of the molecule.

For the exact evaluation of the vibrational partition function, the zero point energy term should incorporate the anharmonic vibrations, while u_i term should make use of harmonic frequencies.

To calculate ω_i from the experimentally observed anharmonic frequencies ν_i , Dennison's rule⁹ has been used :

$$\nu_i = \omega_i (1 - x_i) \quad (14)$$

where x_i is the anharmonicity correction for the i th vibrational mode. The values of x_i for the deuterated and undeuterated species are related by eq. (15)

$$(x_i)_D = (x_i)_H \left(\frac{\nu_i}_D}{\nu_i}_H \right) \quad (15)$$

Thus, from the knowledge of the vibrational frequencies and anharmonicity constants for the various exchanging species, the equilibrium constants K_1 , K_2 , K_3 and K_4 can be calculated.

Results and Discussion

The anharmonic and harmonic frequencies for different deuterated forms of fluoroform, hydrogen, ammonia and water, respectively are given in Tables 1 to 5. Throughout this work, the calculations have been restricted to the low deuterium concentration for all the species taking part in the exchange reactions.

Separation factors for the different isotopic exchange reactions involving the above mentioned species were calculated as a function of temperature over the range -60 to $+80^\circ$. The values of the separation factors, given in Table 6, are found to

TABLE 1—VIBRATIONAL FREQUENCIES OF FLUOROFORM

	CHF ₃		CDF ₃	
	Anharmonic	Harmonic	Anharmonic	Harmonic
ν_1	3034	3160	2293	2380
ν_2	1140	1152	1109	1120
ν_3	700	713	693	617
ν_4	1372	1390	1209	1210
ν_5	1372	1390	1220	1230
ν_6	1152	1154	969	977
ν_7	1152	1154	979	988
ν_8	507	510	504	505
ν_9	507	510	504	505

TABLE 2—VIBRATIONAL FREQUENCIES OF HYDROGEN

	H ₂		HD	
	Anharmonic	Harmonic	Anharmonic	Harmonic
ν_1	4160	4405	3632	3817

TABLE 3—VIBRATIONAL FREQUENCIES OF AMMONIA

	NH ₃		NH ₃ D	
	Anharmonic	Harmonic	Anharmonic	Harmonic
ν_1	3336	3503	3366	3533
ν_2	932	1030	874	951
ν_3	3443	3592	2484	2595
ν_4	3443	3592	3409	3591
ν_5	1626	1690	1608	1657
ν_6	1626	1690	1380	1440

TABLE 4—VIBRATIONAL FREQUENCIES OF METHANE

	CH ₄		CH ₃ D	
	Anharmonic	Harmonic	Anharmonic	Harmonic
ν_1	2915	3036	2200	2268
ν_2	1594	1565	1473	1501
ν_3	1594	1565	1473	1501
ν_4	3019	3144	2970	3091
ν_5	3019	3144	3017	3142
ν_6	3019	3144	3017	3142
ν_7	1306	1332	1158	1178
ν_8	1306	1332	1158	1178
ν_9	1306	1332	1158	1178

TABLE 5—VIBRATIONAL FREQUENCIES OF WATER

	H ₂ O		HDO	
	Anharmonic	Harmonic	Anharmonic	Harmonic
ν_1	3656	3832	2726	2824
ν_2	1594	1648	1403	1441
ν_3	3755	3942	3707	3889

TABLE 6—SEPARATION FACTORS

Temp. °C	α_1	α_2	α_3	α_4
-60	8.856	1.186	1.865	1.635
-50	7.720	1.153	1.732	1.559
-40	6.812	1.124	1.710	1.493
-30	6.076	1.099	1.647	1.436
-20	5.470	1.077	1.591	1.385
-10	4.966	1.057	1.542	1.341
0	4.544	1.039	1.499	1.301
10	4.184	1.023	1.459	1.266
20	3.878	1.009	1.425	1.235
30	3.612	0.996	1.393	1.207
40	3.382	0.984	1.365	1.181
50	3.180	0.974	1.339	1.159
60	3.004	0.964	1.316	1.138
70	2.846	0.956	1.294	1.119
80	2.706	0.948	1.275	1.102

decrease with increasing temperature. As in the case of other isotopic exchange equilibria, the temperature dependence of equilibrium constants, in general, can be represented by eq. (16).

$$\ln K = A/T + B \quad \dots (16)$$

where A and B are constants. A corresponds to the enthalpy of the isotopic exchange reaction, ΔH . The values of ΔH for the reactions (5-8) were found to be

$$\Delta H_1 = -1.245 \text{ kcal/mole.}$$

$$\Delta H_2 = -0.225 \text{ kcal/mole.}$$

$$\Delta H_3 = -0.392 \text{ kcal/mole.}$$

$$\Delta H_4 = -0.405 \text{ kcal/mole.}$$

On comparing the separation factors for all these systems, it can be noticed that fluoroform-hydrogen gives the highest separation factors and if suitable catalyst can be developed, this method should offer the best route to redeuteration.

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